

THE ROLE OF WEBSITES IN TEACHING MEDICAL STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The problem of financing the expensive software financing will appear in modern classes that need to be used information and communication technologies. Educational organizations will only buy and install a package of a specific software. Teachers and students adapt their work to the conditions that do not allow them to fully realize their possibilities. Is there an alternative curriculum that can easily and quickly prepPiling, quickly apply to its class, and that students can show the beauty of using information technology? This problem is solved using new "cloudy" technologies. Currently, web applications can be an effective assistant in the Web 2.0 learning process.

Keywords:

Website, Education, Technology, Knowledge, Cloud Technology

In general, if we answer the following questions:

What are your educational websites?

Educational websites are websites that support the games, videos and others, who serve as a means of improving education or filling class teaching .

What is the importance of education websites?

With the help of these websites, the educational process will be interesting and attractive for the student. This is a fun way to learn gradually.

Today, the widespread web 2 technology is affecting the level of level of education. Web 2.0- (Tim or "Refinition) - Timing Designing Systems Designing Accounting The Systems Designation Method More People More People will be better use of people. Web 2.0 is services that allow users to cooperate and place them online and media data. Such technology is a special place to perform the user ideas. The second generation technology has gained new opportunities, unlike the Web 1.0 (traditional World Wide WEB), which can only view and download the data, and users can view data and

download only. Web 2.0 has become an interactive, free tool to fill and promote the site. Users can at any time correction of the information content of web pages, amend content to content, and controlled it in some cases.

- The features of this environment are:
- Simple use and convenience;
- Ability to create groups and communities on sites;
- Web-generated web;
- Belief in manage the content of the collective of the collective;
- Interactivity;
- Interaction with other websites and services;
- Noun group of private zone;
- Support for all browsers and platforms.

Mobile computers support the tendency to connect to anywhere in their location. This line is widespread after introducing other mobile devices connected to the network via smartphones, tablets and Wi-Fi.

Blogs are interactive diaries, which represent the authors not themselves, but also users filling the content. Mash-UPS: Web pages or applications that combine additional elements from two or more sources. FOAF technology gives them the right to deliver the news and materials of users created. This is the basis of social media.

RSS (Really Simple Syndication) - The literal technology translates as "a real information association" and is used to create news.

Exchange services (user content) - a resource that users are replenished with various music, movies, documents.

Document exchange sites are a service that allows you to create a data, edit, delete data to share software without installing software without setting up your computer. The shining example of this service Writeely.

The social centing includes the exchange of data organized around the content of one or more of the topics. The social complaint of the content includes sites such as Redit, Digg, Pinterest and Instagram.

SaaS is a model that develops a web application, the customer has the right to access the Internet. The advantage of this development is that no costs associated with installation, updating and maintenance of the software operating, operating in it.

In short, the design of the learning process is caused by many opportunities provided by Internet technology. Following the discussion, errors will be re-analyzed and corrected. The fact that in the process of modern education, the importance of the process is shown the efficiency of its educational process, implementation and the issues and problems of use will be discussed.

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